

Precise Electrode Co-alignment in Deep Brain Stimulation Fusing Neuroimaging and Electrophysiology

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Abstract.

Objective: To improve the precision of electrode placement in deep brain stimulation (DBS) by creating a multimodal framework that combines neuroimaging with electrophysiological data, enabling accurate electrode co-alignment.

Approach: We implemented a deep learning-based workflow that combines preoperative magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) and intraoperative microelectrode recordings (MER) for DBS electrode localisation. The workflow includes automated subthalamic nucleus (STN) segmentation using a two-step convolutional neural network (CNN), MER signal classification via a transformer encoder, and spatial co-alignment through a discrete optimisation framework. The entire pipeline is integrated within a 3D Slicer plugin for real-time visualisation and analysis.

Main Results: The proposed method improved electrode localisation accuracy by 0.3 mm, demonstrating improved alignment between electrophysiological and anatomical targets. Real-time visualisation facilitated interactive adjustments, while automated segmentation achieved high Dice similarity scores of 0.62 ± 0.10 for the STN, sufficient for manual refinement.

Significance: This multimodal approach reduces electrode placement errors, incorporates both preoperative and intraoperative data, and provides clinicians with a robust real-time tool to improve DBS results. The integration of neuroimaging and electrophysiology addresses long-standing challenges in DBS, offering a significant step toward personalised and precise neurosurgical interventions.

Keywords: Deep Brain Stimulation, Precise Electrode Localisation, Neuroimaging, Electrophysiology, Subthalamic Nucleus, Optimisation Framework.

1. Introduction

Integrating information obtained from neuroimaging data with the one obtained from invasive electrophysiological recordings is a promising pathway to optimise electrode placement in deep brain stimulation (DBS), particularly to treat neurological disorders such as Parkinson’s disease (PD) [1]. Accurate localisation of the subthalamic nucleus (STN) - a primary target of PD DBS - during surgery is important to maximise clinical outcomes. However, its small size, deep location, and individual anatomical variability pose significant challenges for precise identification and segmentation [2, 3].

Typically, the location of the STN is first visualised using preoperative magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) or computed tomography (CT), which is used for surgical planning, that is, to determine the trajectory of the DBS electrode. While indispensable, neuroimaging techniques have limitations in spatial resolution and may introduce distortions, particularly in deep brain structures such as the STN [4]. Accurate localisation of the STN is further complicated by its low contrast from Substantia Nigra, even if specialised sequences such as T2 or T2* are used [5].

The actual position of the STN during subsequent DBS implantation may deviate from the surgical plan due to several factors, namely stereotactic and co-registration inaccuracies, air entering the skull due to cerebrospinal fluid leakage (pneumocephalus) or postural changes. These aspects may lead to brain shift or non-linear brain deformations, complicating the accurate implantation [6, 7].

For these reasons, many centers use intraoperative invasive microelectrode recordings (MER), which can give clues about inaccuracies of the location provided previously by imaging and deviations from surgical plan and provide a more accurate STN delineation before determining the final stimulation contact positions [8].

MER has long been instrumental in confirming or refining the optimal target site for electrodes that are entered during surgery. Although the procedure can prolong operative time and carries risks such as intracranial haemorrhage and postoperative infections [9, 10, 11], MER continues to offer valuable real-time electrophysiological feedback. Typically, multiple electrodes are entered to probe a larger field of anatomical tissue, and these approaches have shown promise in improving motor outcomes in Parkinson’s disease, especially for symptoms such as tremor and rigidity [12]. Despite its promise and success, MER alone delivers clues that need to be manually integrated by experts that have a strong anatomical understanding and electrophysiological expertise, which typically requires extensive training in the operating room (OR) and depends on signal quality [13].

Together, these challenges – issues in the imaging accuracy when used alone and complicated nature of understanding MER signals – highlight the need for advanced multimodal approaches that integrate electrophysiological information obtained during MER obtained in the OR together with the neuroimaging data collected preoperatively. Discrepancies observed while merging the two sources of information can provide clues about brain shift and valuable insights when determining final implantation position of

the permanent lead. Indeed, such discrepancies have shown to arise: Studies report that MRI can miss vital anatomical details of the STN in up to 20% of cases [14], and different field strengths can shift the apparent boundaries of the STN [15], notably leaving the dorsal margin inconsistently defined. Although high-field magnetic resonance imaging (7T) can reduce lateral border ambiguities, the dorsal boundary remains challenging to precisely pinpoint. In this context, MER still offers critical supplementary information, and optimising its integration with imaging is an active area of research aiming to minimise brain shift effects and other surgical uncertainties.

A recent key advancement in this direction is the Lead-OR platform [16], which spatially visualises MER signals in the stereotactic space defined by MRI (and nuclei segmentations obtained from it) in real time to improve DBS targeting. Here, we build upon and significantly extend this platform by proposing an end-to-end pipeline capable of automatically enhancing electrode localisation by integrating deep learning-based STN segmentations with MER co-alignments. Convolutional neural networks (CNN) have shown strong performance in segmenting subcortical structures, including STN [17, 18]. Our approach employs a two-step CNN model for precise anatomical segmentation, followed by an optimisation framework that aligns MER signals within the segmented STN. Implemented as a 3D Slicer[19] plugin and integrated into Lead-OR, this pipeline provides a robust framework for clinicians and researchers to visualise and analyse neuroimaging and electrophysiological data simultaneously. By reducing target error and accounting for intraoperative brain shift, our method aims to improve electrode targeting and ultimately improve patient outcomes in DBS.

2. Methods

Our aim is to provide surgeons with real-time information about the electrode’s position relative to surrounding anatomical structures during surgery. Ideally, this process should achieve maximum precision and operate in real time. For the purpose of this article, we refer to this process as ‘electrode location’, which should not be confused with similar terms used postoperatively, i.e. in the process of localising electrodes already implanted based on postoperative imaging. In summary, to accurately localise electrodes in real time during DBS surgery, we implemented a shift estimation method that combines deep learning with classical optimisation techniques. This method integrates neuroimaging and electrophysiological data within a structured pipeline, implemented as a 3D Slicer extension. The workflow, outlined in Figure 1, can be broken down into the following components:

1. *STN Segmentation from preoperative MRI:* We developed a two-step convolutional neural network (CNN) model capable of automatically localising and segmenting the subthalamic nucleus (STN) from preoperative MRI scans. This approach generates a 3D surface mesh representation of the STN in stereotactic space. This automated segmentation can be manually refined using published tools available in the Lead-DBS framework [20].

2. *Classification of MER signals*: To address the second requirement, we developed a transformer-based encoder model that processes microelectrode recording (MER) signals, extracting electrophysiological features essential for STN localisation and classifying recording sites as either within or outside the STN.

3. *Co-alignment through discrete optimisation*: To integrate these two sources of information, the segmented STN shapes and classified MER data were combined within an optimisation framework designed to refine electrode placement, thereby compensating for potential brain displacement, such as intraoperative brain shift.

Figure 1: *Overview of the DBS Electrode Co-alignment Framework* This framework combines preoperative MRI with intraoperative MER data, providing enhanced real-time information about electrode positions at any moment during surgery. Top row: The subthalamic nucleus (STN) is segmented from pre-operative MRI data, with optional manual refinements applied to enhance anatomical accuracy. Bottom row: Intraoperative MER signals are automatically classified into inside/outside STN groups. The co-alignment framework then aligns MER-based classifications and location with the refined STN segmentation.

2.1. Data and labelling

Five data subsets from three data sources were used to train and validate the different steps of the method, summarised in Table 1.

2.1.1. *OASIS-3 MRI Dataset* We used the publicly available OASIS-3 dataset [21] to train and evaluate our segmentation model. OASIS-3 includes high-resolution structural

magnetic resonance imaging, along with cognitive and clinical evaluations from 1,378 participants, which include individuals who are cognitively healthy, have mild cognitive impairment (MCI) or are diagnosed with Alzheimer’s disease (AD).

For this study, we focussed on T1 and T2-weighted MRI scans acquired using 1.5T and 3T MRI scanners. The dataset includes individuals aged 42 to 95 years. We trained our CNN model using segmentation labels generated by P-Brain [17]. For validation, the STN in the test set was manually segmented using ITK-SNAP [22].

2.1.2. External Validation: IXI Dataset For external validation of our MRI segmentation model, we used a manually labelled subset of the IXI dataset, which was previously used to develop the DISTAL atlas [23]. This data set includes T1- and T2-weighted MRI scans from individuals without known health conditions, acquired using 1.5T and 3T MRI scanners.

A cohort of 22 individuals (14 women, 8 men) aged 55 to 70 years (mean 63.8 ± 4.3 years) was selected to align with clinical populations seen in DBS. The STNs were manually segmented, primarily using T2-weighted images for better accuracy. These manual labels, including those for adjacent structures, were supplied by the original authors. A detailed description of the labeling procedure is available in [23].

2.1.3. PRAGUE-MER Dataset The PRAGUE-MER dataset was used to train and evaluate the MER classification model. It contains MER recordings collected from 112 Parkinson’s disease patients undergoing DBS surgery.

MER recordings were performed using one to five tungsten microelectrodes in a cross configuration, with a 2mm spacing between the electrodes. The electrodes advanced by 0.5mm between the recording positions. Ten-second recordings were collected at each position using the Leadpoint (Medtronic, MN) system, sampled at 24kHz and bandpass filtered between 500Hz and 5000Hz.

Each recording position was manually labelled by the surgical team as STN or non-STN, forming the basis for classification.

2.1.4. Prague Multimodal Dataset (PD Patients Undergoing DBS) The Prague Multimodal Dataset consists of 18 participants with PD who underwent subthalamic nucleus deep brain stimulation (STN-DBS). This group included 8 women and 10 men, aged 47 to 70 years (mean 58.8 ± 7.6 years).

Among these participants, 12 had intraoperative O-arm CT (OARM) scans, but only 11 were used for co-alignment validation due to imaging issues. The dataset includes 3T T2-weighted MRI, 1.5T T1-weighted MRI, O-arm CT (OARM), Microelectrode recordings (MER).

MER data were recorded and labelled consistently with the PRAGUE-MER dataset. Unlike PRAGUE-MER, this dataset includes both electrophysiological and imaging data, allowing for co-alignment validation.

Table 1: Datasets used for training and testing of segmentation, microelectrode signal classification, and co-alignment.

Usage	Data source	Size & Composition	Modalities	Notes
Segmentation train	OASIS-3	1,366 selected subjects	T1, T2, pBrain automatic labels	OASIS-3 contains various conditions including neurodegenerative
Segmentation test	OASIS-3	10 subjects manually labeled	T1, T2, Manual labels	Manual labels by a trained expert
	DISTAL (IXI subset)	22 subjects manually labeled	T1, T2, Manual labels	Manual labels by Ewert [23]
MER train	PRAGUE-MER	112 PD patients, 935 microelectrodes	MER, MER labels	MER signals labelled intra-operatively by a neurologist
MER test	PRAGUE-Multimodal	30 PD patients	T1, T2, MER	Subjects without STN recordings excluded; total 18 subjects, 28 sides
Co-alignment test	PRAGUE-Multimodal	12 PD patients	T1, T2, MER, OARM	1 subject excluded; 4 missing unilateral MER/MRI; 17 STNs in total

2.2. Model for Subcortical Segmentation

We used a cascaded neural network architecture for segmentation, dividing the process into two stages. The first stage involves predicting the centre-of-mass coordinates of the STN, while the second stage focusses on delineating its boundaries to generate a 3D surface mesh.

2.2.1. MRI Preprocessing The preprocessing pipeline we employed follows the approach outlined in our previous work [24].

To standardise intensity values, we applied fuzzy c-means clustering combined with white matter intensity normalisation [25] to ensure intensity consistency between participants. White matter masks were generated using the deep Atropos algorithm [26].

All brain images were linearly co-registered in the Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) space [27] for spatial alignment. This co-registration step maintained anatomical accuracy by applying the same transformations to both imaging data and corresponding labels, ensuring consistency and comparability across subjects.

2.2.2. STN Center Detection The center detection employs a CNN-based brain extraction method from ANTs [28], improving segmentation accuracy and processing efficiency. Detailed descriptions of the general preprocessing pipeline can be found in our previous publication [24].

A region of interest (ROI) for the STN was defined in the MNI space, extending 3 mm along each axis to account for inter-subject variability. Symmetry-based processing mirrored one hemisphere onto the other, allowing both STNs to be processed with a single model.

Within this ROI, a CNN-based model predicts the centre coordinates of the STN

(x, y, z) , scaled to a range $[0,1]$. The network consists of convolutional blocks with ReLU activation and max-pooling layers, while a Sigmoid activation in the final layer constrains the output within the normalised range (network scheme is in the Supplementary Materials).

2.2.3. STN Shape Segmentation The next stage involved the segmentation of the STN. Following the initial estimate of the STN centre, we define a refined ROI around this estimated position. For the segmentation, we then employ a CNN model with architecture similar to that used in centre detection, consisting of convolutional blocks followed by max-pooling layers.

The network was trained to predict the weights of the principal component analysis (PCA) representing the shape of the STN as a standard 3D mesh shape primitives [24]. This PCA-based approach provides a compact representation of shape variability around the STN centre, allowing efficient learning and accurate predictions.

To improve segmentation accuracy, we incorporate the Warp Drive toolbox [20], which allows manual refinement of the STN shape. This allows clinicians to refine automated segmentation, ensuring a more accurate representation of the STN. The adjusted STN shape is then used in the co-alignment pipeline to improve alignment with recorded electrode positions, reducing errors in shift estimation.

2.3. Co-alignment of Microelectrode Recording within MRI-based STN

In this step, the segmented 3D contour of the STN — optionally refined manually and derived from preoperative MRI — is automatically aligned with intraoperative MER data to obtain a more precise estimate of electrode positioning within and around the STN. This alignment process involves two key components: MER signal classification and spatial optimisation of electrode positions.

2.3.1. MER Signal Classification First, we developed a classification model to identify electrode positions within the STN, based on normalised root mean square (NRMS) values extracted at each recording step from the MER [29]. NRMS values, adapted from methods used in the Lead-OR platform [16], provide a quantitative measure of neuronal activity and are highly effective in characterising STN signals [30].

We implemented a transformer encoder model [31] to classify microelectrode recordings (MERs) as originating from inside or outside the STN. The transformer architecture is particularly well suited to modelling sequential dependencies, making it ideal for handling structured MER sequences acquired along each microelectrode trajectory. In contrast to methods that classify each depth independently, the transformer encoder integrates contextual information across multiple recording depths to improve classification robustness.

Our formulation assumes that classification at a given depth x_i may depend on signals from adjacent depths $\{x_{i-k}, \dots, x_i, \dots, x_{i+k}\}$, without requiring causality

constraints (i.e., both past and future inputs are available during classification). The model was trained using cross-entropy loss on expert-labelled MER segments.

2.3.2. Electrode-STN Co-alignment To improve the spatial consistency between intraoperative electrophysiological signals and preoperative imaging, we implemented a co-alignment framework based on spatial optimisation. The aim is to minimise discrepancies between the MRI-derived STN mesh and the classification of MER sites as within or outside the STN.

The optimisation problem is formalised using a cost function $C(\mathbf{x}, s, \alpha)$ that evaluates the quality of a given spatial transformation. Specifically, we estimate a shift vector $s \in \mathbb{R}^3$ and an STN scaling factor $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}_+$ that improve the alignment between the MER points and the anatomical STN label. Optimisation penalises inconsistencies between MER classification (STN vs. non-STN) and their spatial inclusion within the transformed STN mesh.

The optimal transformation parameters are obtained by solving:

$$(\hat{s}, \hat{\alpha}) = \arg \min_{s, \alpha} C(\mathbf{x}, s, \alpha)$$

Let \mathbf{x}_i denote the original coordinates of the i -th MER recording, and let $y_i \in \{0, 1\}$ be its classification label. Let y_i^* indicate whether the transformed recording position $\mathbf{x}_i - s$ is within the scaled mesh $\alpha\mathcal{M}$. Then the objective function is defined as:

$$C(\mathbf{x}, s, \alpha) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \delta(y_i \neq y_i^*) \cdot d(\mathbf{x}_i - s, \alpha\mathcal{M})$$

where:

- $\delta(y_i \neq y_i^*)$ is an indicator function that equals 1 when the classification and mesh inclusion disagree (i.e., a misalignment), and 0 otherwise.
- $d(\cdot, \alpha\mathcal{M})$ denotes the shortest Euclidean distance from the point to the surface of the scaled STN mesh.

Minimising this cost enforces anatomical and electrophysiological overlap. Detailed step-by-step explanation of the criterion calculation is provided in the Supplementary Material. Powell’s optimisation method [32] was chosen for its robustness in non-differentiable optimisation problems, suitable for handling discrete inclusion logic and geometric distance functions.

This approach reduces manual adjustments during DBS planning and improves anatomical precision, accounting for individual anatomical variability and recording noise in the MER signal.

3. Results

The primary outcome of our work is a platform that enables automatic processing and real-time co-alignment of MRI and MER data. We developed multiple extension

modules within 3D Slicer to assist surgeons with planning and visualisation tasks. While based on the Lead-OR pipeline [16], our implementation significantly extends its functionality by introducing a pipeline capable of estimating the optimal transformation for aligning electrodes within the STN. Below, we provide validation results for the individual processing steps.

3.1. STN Shape Segmentation Results

In the first step, generate a patient-specific STN shape based on imaging data. The effectiveness of our segmentation approach is shown in Table 2, with Dice similarity scores indicating the agreement between automated and manually refined segmentations. Dice score of 0.589 (± 0.112) for the left STN and 0.619 (± 0.102) for the right STN on the OASIS test set, and 0.578 (± 0.101) for the left STN and 0.609 (± 0.095) for the right STN on the IXI dataset. As seen from the results, the segmentation accuracy is comparable to that of the pBrains model [17] when applied to the dataset used. To ensure accurate shape representation, manual refinement using WarpDrive was applied in the next step when needed to correct discrepancies in automated segmentation.

Method	Data	STN left	STN right
<i>pBrains</i>		0.862	0.867
<i>pBrains (OASIS labels)</i>	3T	0.572(0.105)	0.583(0.107)
<i>CNN method (OASIS labels)</i>	3T	0.589(0.112)	0.619(0.102)
<i>CNN method (Evert IXI labels)</i>	3T	0.578(0.101)	0.609(0.095)

Table 2: Comparison of segmentation accuracy (Dice coefficient) for different methods and datasets.

3.2. MER Signal Classification Results

In the automated MER classification task, evaluated on the *MER-test* dataset, our model achieved an accuracy of 0.90, a sensitivity of 0.85, and a specificity of 0.91 in the test set compared to expert-based labelling – see results in Figure 2. The classification is closely aligned with manual STN labels, particularly in regions with high levels of spiking activity. While the overall accuracy remains high, the slightly lower sensitivity suggests that certain STN regions may be misclassified as outside, despite being within the STN according to expert judgement.

Figure 2: *MER energy and automated classification of neural MER Recordings on the Prague-Multimodal dataset.* (a) Heatmap illustrating normalised energy levels (NRMS) across electrodes and recording positions. The color gradient represents energy values, with red boxes indicating manual labels of STN based on NRMS. (b) Corresponding illustration of results of the automated classification of microelectrode recordings (MER, STN in yellow), with red boxes indicating manually labeled STN boundaries (c) Boxplots summarising the overall performance of the classification algorithm in terms of accuracy (mean = 0.90) and sensitivity (mean = 0.85), with medians, interquartile ranges, and outliers displayed.

3.3. Electrode-STN Coalignment Results

In the next step, we applied the optimisation procedure to perform the co-alignment between the MER and STN surface to the coalignment-test dataset. Figure 3 illustrates an example case in which the electrode displacement is shown before and after applying

the automatic shift correction – shifting the MER electrodes to match their likely position relative to the imaging-derived segmentation of the STN, positioned according to the surgical plan.

Alternatively, the developed module supports an alternative approach that involves translation and scaling of the segmented STN shape to better match the electrode recordings. This is illustrated in Figure 3, with additional examples provided in the Supplementary Materials (available online).

Figure 3: Comparison of electrode placement before and after co-alignment. (a) 2D slice showing the initial planned electrode positions (blue circles) relative to the subthalamic nucleus (STN) contour (yellow) before co-alignment. A view along the electrode trajectory with interpolated perpendicular MRI cross-section. (b) 3D view of the STN mesh and electrode trajectories prior to co-alignment, illustrating initial misalignment. (c) 2D slice after co-alignment, demonstrating improved alignment of electrodes (blue circles) within the STN contour (yellow). (d) 3D rendering of the STN mesh and electrode trajectories after co-alignment, illustrating improved spatial alignment. An animated version is available in the online supplement.

To validate the co-alignment procedure, we applied the full pipeline to the *coalignment-test* dataset with maximum shift set to 3 mm and maximum STN scaling

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: (a) A three-dimensional rendering of the segmented subthalamic nucleus (STN) before (lime green) and after (aquamarine) spatial alignment, with the electrode trajectories shown in purple. (b) The box-and-whisker plot compares accuracy of microelectrode placement within STN before and after the STN shift. Overall, these images illustrate how spatial realignment improves the electrodes’ placement within the adjusted STN.

factor $\pm 20\%$ from original STN. Then, we measured the distance between the co-aligned (shifted) electrode positions and their corresponding trajectories identified by intraoperative OARM imaging (see Supplementary Data for details). We chose this approach as the depth information could not be retrieved from the OARM data due to non-clear depiction of the electrode tip in the imaging data. Using manually refined STN labels, the average local error across 17 cases decreased by 0.3 mm following co-alignment, improving from 1.2 ± 0.6 mm to 0.9 ± 0.5 mm ($p < 0.02$). The accuracy of MER site placement within the imaging-defined STN improved after co-alignment from 0.72 ± 0.07 to 0.88 ± 0.06 Figure 4b.

We thus evaluated all individual components of the processing pipeline, as well as finally the full processing using the multimodal dataset.

4. Discussion

Building on the Lead-OR platform, our DBS Co-alignment toolbox improves the understanding of the spatial relationship between recorded MER signals and the STN by incorporating co-alignment transformations. To achieve this, we perform segmentation of the STN from preoperative MRI, with the possibility of manual refinement, automatically identify the MER as STN or non-STN and then perform

a co-alignment to refine anatomical placement information of the electrode in real time.

Although segmentation was not our primary focus, our method achieved a Dice similarity score of 0.6. This result closely matches the performance of pBrains [17] evaluated in our dataset, which also achieved a Dice score of approximately 0.6, which is significantly lower than the values originally reported by the authors. This indicates that pBrains does not outperform our approach under the same imaging conditions, and the observed discrepancy likely stems from differences in data quality and acquisition protocols between datasets. Another framework, DBSegment [18], reported a Dice score of 0.89; however, their evaluation was based on a coregistration-derived gold standard and relied solely on T1-weighted images. While T1-weighted contrast may suffice for initial segmentation, achieving patient-specific accuracy requires T2-weighted imaging to capture finer anatomical details. As our segmentation model was trained using automated labels from the pBrains algorithm rather than manual annotations, this may have introduced a potential bias. To enhance accuracy and reliability, expert-labelled data is essential for validation and refinement; however, such datasets are currently scarce due to the time-consuming and labour-intensive nature of manual annotation. Enhancing STN segmentation would further improve our co-alignment results. To support this, we offer open-access segmentation resources within 3D Slicer (available at: https://github.com/IVarha/slicer_dbs_modules) and recommend manual refinement using tools such as WarpDrive [20] when needed.

For the MER classification, we used the RMS feature provided by Lead-OR. Our model achieved an accuracy of 0.90, which is slightly better but comparable to the 0.85 accuracy reported by others [33] to classify recordings as inside or outside the STN. Other studies have explored different feature sets and classification approaches. For instance, a model incorporating 25 features, including both spike-dependent and spike-independent characteristics, combined with an ensemble tree classifier, achieved 0.94 accuracy in STN identification [34]. Although such approaches may further refine classification performance, processing a large number of features in real-time remains a complex computational challenge.

In terms of existing co-localisation approaches Lourens et al.[35] fitted an STN atlas to MER positions and reported an accuracy of 0.93 in placing MER sites within the atlas-defined STN, which is comparable to our reported value of 0.88. However, their approach allowed for 10mm of displacement, whereas our model limits shift to a maximum of 3mm. This constraint aligns more closely with clinical observations, as shifts exceeding 4mm [36] are rarely observed in surgeries and can often be mitigated with proper electrode placement techniques [37, 38]. Additionally, our method does not incorporate rotations, further constraining the alignment process. Similarly, Lujan et al. [39] demonstrated that their optimisation-based atlas fit outperformed manual expert fits and AC/PC scaling, achieving 0.81 precision in aligning MER sites with the atlas. Both methods rely on atlas-based fitting, whereas our approach provides a more flexible, patient-specific refinement by directly correcting the MRI-MER misalignment. Furthermore, our study incorporates a comparison with intraoperative O-arm CT imaging, providing

an objective reference to evaluate alignment accuracy.

Our results show that electrodes remained within the STN after co-alignment, with an average error reduction of 0.3 mm compared to the OARM trajectory, underscoring the reliability of our co-alignment framework. However, STN segmentation accuracy remained a critical factor that influenced precision, highlighting the need for high-quality imaging. Specifically, optimised high-resolution T2 sequences should significantly reduce placement uncertainty, further improving the alignment process.

A crucial aspect of our study is the reliance on manual refinement in cases where automatic segmentation did not perform well. When applying the co-alignment procedure to automatically segmented STN surfaces, we did not observe a statistically significant improvement in electrode displacement. This may indicate limitations in our dataset, including the relatively small number of subjects available for analysis. Expanding the study to multiple centres could provide a more diverse and reliable dataset, ultimately improving the generalisability of our findings.

Establishing a definitive ground truth for shift estimation remains challenging due to multiple sources of error in clinical data. Differences in imaging modalities (O arm, T1, T2), co-registration inaccuracies, intraoperative brain shift, electrode bending, and postsurgical electrode migration all contribute to uncertainty. Furthermore, deviations between the planned and actual electrode trajectories, as observed in postoperative imaging, suggest that mechanical factors during insertion may introduce further variability. As a result, our toolbox is best used as a guidance tool to assess electrode placement within the STN.

5. Conclusion

This study introduces a robust and user-friendly visualisation and processing toolbox that integrates MER data with patient-specific anatomical information obtained from MRI. Our approach leverages a transformer encoder-based classification model to process NRMS features extracted from MER signals, enhancing the precision of electrode placement. Powell’s optimisation method is used to align electrophysiological recordings with segmented STN, improving spatial accuracy in targeting DBS. This multimodal framework provides valuable information to support accurate and informed decision-making during surgery.

Designed for researchers and clinicians, our toolbox enables seamless co-alignment of MER and MRI data, effectively addressing critical challenges in DBS electrode targeting.

While initial results are encouraging, large-scale validation across multiple clinical centres is essential to thoroughly evaluate the robustness of our approach, especially in accounting for intraoperative brain shifts and variability in electrode placement. Future work should prioritise the integration of clinical outcome measures, enhancement of methodological precision, and the execution of prospective clinical trials to validate long-term clinical effectiveness.

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7. Ethics Statement

This study was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. This human study was approved by Ethics Committee of the General University Hospital in Prague under number 59/18. All adult participants provided written informed consent to participate in this study.

8. Data Availability

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are owned by a third party and the terms of use prevent public distribution. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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